

Validity and Reliability of The Turkish-Adapted School Participant Empowerment Scale (SPES) for Teachers with the PLS-SEM Approach*

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Abstract

The importance of empowering school participants is increasing day by day. A school with empowered teachers can take more confident steps towards future education. Thus, it is important to determine the empowerment level of teachers as an important stakeholder of the school. The main purpose of this research is to adopt a measurement tool developed to determine the level of empowerment of school participants to Turkish school culture. For this, the School Participants Empowerment Scale (SPES) was used. The original scale has six factors (decision making, professional development, status, self-efficacy, autonomy, impact) and 38 items. There are n=108 teachers working in different types of public schools (preschool, primary school, secondary school, and high school) in the sample group of the research. Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach was adopted in the adaptation process of the scale. Smart PLS 3.2.8 program was used in the analysis of the research data. For validity and reliability on the data, 2nd level Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed by means of the Partial Least Square (PLS) method. At the end of the research; It was understood that the Turkish version of the scale generally preserved the original six-factor scale structure. But, it was determined that 9 items that could not fit the structural model should be removed from the Turkish version. The Turkish version of the scale adapted for teachers can be used in the context of Turkey as a six-factor and 29-item scale. Findings show that the scale exhibits good fit characteristics of the PLS-SEM approach.

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Introduction

The idea of empowering school participants has always been popular in academia since the 1980s. In this regard, the group whose priority is most discussed among school participants is teachers. The belief that "the academic success of a school with strong teachers can also increase" strengthens these discussions even more. According to McLaughlin et al. (1992) teacher empowerment became a slogan in the late 1980s. In this context, Lightfoot explains empowerment as a set of opportunities a person has for autonomy, responsibility, choice, and authority (Lightfoot, 1986). Thus, Browder (1994) defines teacher empowerment as a set of activities or tools that enhance the professional status of teachers. He suggests that empowerment can increase a teacher's self-

esteem and knowledge of the field and pedagogy. Thus, colleague cooperation in schools is further encouraged. Because in reality, school bureaucracy limits teacher autonomy as it remains unchanged. Melenyzer (1990) explains empowerment as the opportunity and confidence of the teacher to influence the way he/she performs his/her profession by acting according to his/her own ideas. According to him, empowerment has positive effects on teachers such as increasing professional attitude, taking responsibility in the decision-making process, and more participation in the process.

The literature, see that teacher empowerment has positive effects on educational environments, especially school management. There are different studies that associate teacher empowerment in schools with

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many different topics. Among these studies, for example; organizational behavior (Ahmed, 2021), job satisfaction (Ahrari, 2021; Rinehart & Short, 1994), leadership and conflict management (Short & Johnson, 1994), school climate (Short & Rinehart, 1993), organizational learning (Marks & Louis, 1999), school reform (Avidov-Ungar & Arviv-Elyashiv, 2018; Whitaker & Moses, 1990), organizational change (Hejaz et al., 2019), well-being (Yusoff & Tengku-Ariffin, 2020), organizational behavior (Tindowen, 2019), job engagement (Vesudevan, 2021), the culture of innovation (Gil et al., 2018), perception of effective school (Gülşen & Çelik, 2021), power relationship (Elmazi, 2018) and quality of education (Yunus et al., 2021) are available. So, it can state that teacher empowerment, especially teacher autonomy, has many different dimensions that need to examine from an administrative point of view.

These dimensions are listed by Klecker and Loadman as decision making, collegiality/collaboration, professional knowledge, self-efficacy, autonomy, and teachers' status in the classroom. According to them, teachers need to get knowledge beyond content knowledge and pedagogy for their effective participation in school restructuring. In fact, teachers' professional knowledge should be able to form a comprehensive basis both in the philosophy and educational processes of the change model adopted by their schools (Klecker & Loadman, 1996). According to Short (1994), for teacher empowerment: there are six interrelated dimensions: participation in the decision-making process, teacher influence, teacher status, autonomy, professional development opportunities, and teacher self-efficacy (Short, 1994). Again, according to him, each of these dimensions has different meanings in itself (Short, 1992):

- *Decision making*: It refers to the participation of teachers in critical decisions that affect their work in schools.
- *Professional development*: It describes the perceptions of teachers that the school they work in offers them opportunities for continuous professional learning, development, and improvement of their own skills.

- *Status*: Indicates teachers' belief that they receive professional respect and admiration from their colleagues.
- *Self-efficacy*: Teachers' perceptions that they are influential on students' learning and that they have abilities and skills to help them learn.
- *Autonomy*: Teachers' feelings of control over their ability to make certain decisions about timing, curriculum, textbooks, and instructional planning in their work.
- *Impact*: Refers to teachers' perceptions that the school has an impact on the working climate.

In summary, Short (1992) explains that teacher empowerment includes six important dimensions. Teachers should definitely take part in the decisions that affect them in their working life at school. Thus, the decisions to take can place more in the school. A school climate that supports the professional development of the teacher will strengthen him. This can also increase its prestigious status among its peers. The impact of a teacher with high self-efficacy on students and the educational process should not underestimate. With the sense of control that such a teacher will feel, the tendency to take risks in their studies may increase. In this context, teachers will be an important part of the school's empowerment process by displaying more autonomous educational behaviors. Thus, it can state that there may be a direct relationship between school empowerment and teacher empowerment (Short, 1994). In this context, teacher empowerment and servant leadership at school (Afaq et al., 2017), effective school management (Rafique & Akhtar, 2020), internal organizational characteristics (Kang et al., 2021), ethical behaviors expected from teachers at school, school environment (Kusumaningrum et al., 2019) and the roles of school administrators (Balyer et al., 2017) are also found in studies that establish a relationship at different levels.

So, Martin and Crossland (2000) claimed that teacher empowerment in schools is important for school climate and increased sense of teacher competence, but has no effect on student achievement. In fact, according to

Sprague (1992), teacher empowerment distracts attention from the individual and psychological characteristics of teachers or their administrative behaviors in the classroom. It puts teachers under the influence of political, socio-cultural, and organizational forces that constrain them in trying to fulfill their duties (Sprague, 1992). In other words, it is also important to consider teacher empowerment from a critical perspective. It would be a mistake to think that teacher empowerment is the solution to every school-related problem.

According to Kahraman and Çelik (2020), despite all the international literature on teacher empowerment, the concept of teacher empowerment is still a controversial issue in Turkey. In addition, it has been predicted that the number of studies on the subject is not sufficient. In particular, it has been suggested to conduct research on the psychological and structural empowerment of teachers. In addition, although there are scale development studies (Özkan Hidroğlu & Tanrıöğen, 2020; Puskulluoglu & Altinkurt, 2017) that measure teacher empowerment structurally in the national literature, the number of scales that deal with teacher empowerment with the dimension of psychological empowerment is less. At this point, it was decided to adapt the “School Participants Empowerment Scale” (Short & Rinehart, 1992), which is thought to measure teacher empowerment with the dimension of psychological empowerment, into Turkish in order to assist researches/researchers on the subject. Thus, it is thought that an important contribution will be made to teacher empowerment research in Turkey. Therefore, the main purpose of this research is to adapt the Turkish version of the “School Participants Empowerment Scale” to the current school culture.

Method

This research is a scale adaptation study. The literature review showed that the “School Participants Empowerment Scale” developed

by Short and Rinehart (1992) had not adapted into Turkish before. For this reason, it predicted that the scale could adapt to Turkish and use it to determine the empowerment levels of teachers at school. PLS-SEM approach was used in the adaptation process of the scale. Because, it understood that the PLS-SEM approach instead of CB-SEM gives stronger results and can so preferred, especially for studies with small sample sizes (Afthanorhan, 2013; Hair Jr et al., 2017; Memon et al., 2021). This approach has been developed by Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle and Gudergan (2018) and Vinzi, Trinchera and Amato (2010) as a covariance-based structural equation modeling method that allows estimating complex cause-effect relationship models on latent variables. It has two sub-models, the measurement model and the structural model. While the measurement model explains the relationship between observed and latent variables; the structural model reveals the degree of significance of the relationships between latent variables (Hair et al., 2018; Vinzi et al., 2010).

The most important advantage of the PLS-SEM approach is that it offers the opportunity to work even with very small sample groups (Kock & Hadaya, 2018). Because the sample size is an important problem for the CB-SEM approach. Yet, according to Lowry and Gaskin (2014), this does not apply to studies in which the PLS-SEM approach is adopted. Because both the normal distribution condition is not required and a sample of 10 times the total number of paths between the latent variables is enough for the analysis. The Bootstrap Method (Bootstrapping), which include in this approach process, is a method that offers a wider resampling and randomization opportunity (Efron & Tibshirani, 1993). Thanks to this method, it is possible to estimate the sampling distribution of almost every statistic by using random sampling methods (Varian, 2005). The measurement model of the research is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Measurement model for adapted scale

[DM: Decision Making, ST: Status, PG: Professional Development, SE: Self-efficacy, AU: Autonomy, IM: Impact, SPES: School Participants Empowerment Scale]

In Figure 1, it is seen that the measurement model of the research consists of six sub-dimensions in total. These dimensions belong to the original scale; decision making (DM), status (ST), professional development (PG), self-efficacy (SE), autonomy (AU), and impact (IM). The model consists of 38 scale items in total. The total number of paths between latent variables in the measurement model is six.

Participants

The participant group of the research consists of n=108 teachers working in public schools in Muş. Ten participants from this group, who participated in the research took part in the scale adaptation process. Data analysis in the research was carried out with the response of the 98 teachers. According to this, 25 of the participants are male and 73 of them are female. Their average age is 33.3. Secondary school teachers (59.2%) represent the largest group among the participants. This is followed by the

participants working in primary school (24.5%), high school (12.2%), and preschool (4.1%). The number of experienced teachers (11 years and above) with professional seniority is 37.8%. There are also teachers with a seniority of 0-5 years (36.7%) and participants with a seniority of 6-10 years (25.5%).

Features of the original scale

The original scale adapted in the study is the “School Participants Empowerment Scale” developed by Short and Rinehart (1992). This scale consists of 38 items and six factors. Factors of the scale; decision making (10 items), professional development (6 items), status (6 items), self-efficacy (6 items), autonomy (4 items), and influence (6 items). The calculated confidence value (CA) is .94. Factor loads vary between .81 and .89. The sample group is secondary school teachers (Short & Rinehart, 1992).

Scale adaptation procedure

First, “permission to adapt the scale” got by the researchers who developed the scale before the adaptation process of the original scale started (Appendix C). The original scale, for which ethical adaptation permission was obtained, was translated into Turkish by the researcher. Then, the Turkish version of the scale was translated back into English by two English instructors. Afterward, a comparison was made between the English and Turkish texts of the scale meaning relationship. At the end of the comparison, the adapted Turkish version of the scale was given its final form. The adapted scale was also reviewed by an educational sciences expert. Finally, the Turkish version of the scale was read and responded to by 10 teachers who participated in the research. Teachers stated that the scale items were generally clear and understandable. Based on the feedback given by the participants, it was decided that the adapted Turkish version of the scale was ready for application (Appendix A). Likert ranges of “1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=undecided, 4=agree, 5=strongly agree” were used for the responses of the participants.

Data collection process

Appropriate/accidental sampling method was used in the study. The data collection process was carried out online (<https://124.im/3dUH8j>) due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The adapted scale form was sent to a total of 127 teachers via a WhatsApp group. The number of responses returned is 118. Among these answers, the answers of n=98 participants were deemed appropriate for evaluation. In other words, the return rate of the adapted scale is 77.2%.

Data analysis

According to Ghasemy et al. (2020), both measurement and structural model analyzes must be performed in research based on the PLS-SEM approach. For the validity and reliability of the model; Factor loading values of the measurement model, mean explained variance (AVE), composite reliability (CR), Cronbach Alpha (CA), rho_A, Fornell-Larcker, HTMT, and t-statistic analyzes should be performed. For the structural model of the study, standardized factor loading values and

VIF findings should be reported (Ghasemy et al., 2020). In this context, the measurement model was tested first for the analysis of the adapted scale. Then, the analyzes were completed using the Bootstrap Method for the structural model (N=5000).

Results

To test the convergence and divergence validity of the scale, preliminary analyzes were carried out on the measurement model created within the scope of the research. Within the scope of these analyzes, t-test statistics for each item in the scale were examined (>1.96). Then, items with valid indicator coefficients were determined for each sub-dimension of the scale ($>.70$). After this process, the average values of the valid indicator coefficient loads were calculated ($>.70$). Then, the average variance extracted (AVE) values for each sub-dimension of the scale were examined ($>.50$). Also, the composite reliability (CR), Cronbach Alpha (CA), and rho_A values were also analyzed ($>.70$). Besides, Fornell-Larcker, HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations), and latent variable correlation values were also compared for the measurement model. The findings obtained in all these analyzes are presented in Table 1 and Table 2. It is possible to examine the values obtained at the end of the Bootstrapping analysis performed for the structural model analyzes of the scale from Figure 2 and Table 2. According to Table 1, it is understood that the Fornell-Larcker, HTMT and latent variable correlation values calculated for the measurement model of the scale are within the appropriate ranges predicted by the PLS-SEM literature. It is seen that the Fornell-Larcker values of the measurement model are in the range of .79-.87 and are higher than all correlation values (.26-.79) of the latent variables in the columns and rows they entered. Also, it can be stated that the HTMT values of the measurement model vary in the range of .29-.88. The first findings of the measurement model show that there is a good agreement between the sub-dimensions of the generally adapted scale (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Franke & Sarstedt, 2019; Henseler et al., 2015). Besides, other values calculated for the convergent and divergent validity of the measurement model and showing good agreement with the measurement model are shared in Table 2.

Table 1.

Fornell-Larcker, HTMT and latent variable correlation values of the measurement model

	AU	DM	IM	PG	SE	ST
AU	.87					
DM	.26 (.29)	.79				
IM	.39 (.43)	.56 (.61)	.85			
PG	.36 (.43)	.58 (.68)	.67 (.74)	.86		
SE	.46 (.50)	.64 (.71)	.79 (.88)	.48 (.54)	.81	
ST	.51 (.59)	.59 (.65)	.77 (.82)	.75 (.85)	.63 (.69)	.82

Figure 2. Bootstrap method results of structural model for adapted scale (N=5000)

In Figure 2, the program screen output obtained at the end of the Bootstrapping analysis of the structural model for the adapted scale form is seen. It can be said that there is a significant relationship between the sub-dimensions of the scale adapted into Turkish and the whole scale ($t > 1.96$). For more detailed results of the structural model (see Table 2.).

According to Table 2, it can be said that the preconditions for convergence and discriminant validity for the measurement model adapted into Turkish were met to a large extent. But, after discriminant validity analysis, 9 of the original scale items (dm_4, dm_8, dm_9, dm_10, pg_11, pg_12, pg_13, au_30, im_34) were excluded from the model because they did not have enough indicator coefficients ($> .704$). It can also be stated that the calculated

AVE, CR, rho_A and Cronbach Alpha values show an acceptable and good fit for the discriminant validity of the measurement model (AVE $> .50$; CR, rho_A, CA $> .70$). Thus, for the structural model obtained as a result of the analysis of the measurement model, 2nd level Confirmatory Factor Analysis (DFA) was performed with the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method. When the t-statistic, standardized factor loads and VIF (variance inflation factor) values obtained as a result of the analysis of the structural model are examined, it is understood that these values are acceptable and the structural model has a good fit. In other words, it can be stated that the structural model of the Turkish version of the "School Participants Empowerment Scale", which consists of 29 items and six factors, is a valid and reliable model.

Table 2.

Summary of measurement and structural model characteristics of the Turkish version of the school participants empowerment scale adapted for teachers

Structural Model Measurement Criteria	Decision Making	Professional Development	Status	Self-efficacy	Autonomy	Impact	Comments for the Turkish Version of the Scale
1. Validity of the Measurement Model							
1.1. Convergent Validity							
t-Statistically significant items (>1.96)	dm_1, dm_2, dm_3, dm_4, dm_5, dm_6, dm_7, dm_8, dm_9, dm_10	pg_11, pg_12, pg_13, pg_14, pg_15, pg_16	st_17, st_18, st_19, st_20, st_21, st_22	se_23, se_24, se_25, se_26, se_27, se_28	au_29, au_30, au_31, au_32	im_33, im_34, im_35, im_36, im_37, im_38	At this stage, there are 38 items that are compatible with the original scale.
1.2. Discriminant Validity							
Items with valid indicator coefficient (>.70)	dm_1 (.81), dm_2 (.78), dm_3 (.78), dm_5 (.79), dm_6 (.83), dm_7 (.72)	pg_14 (.88), pg_15 (.91), pg_16 (.78)	st_17 (.80), st_18 (.72), st_19 (.87), st_20 (.78), st_21 (.87), st_22 (.89)	se_23 (.83), se_24 (.79), se_25 (.79), se_26 (.86), se_27 (.76), se_28 (.85)	au_29 (.84), au_31 (.88), au_32 (.88)	im_33 (.74), im_35 (.80), im_36 (.88), im_37 (.90), im_38 (.92)	Of the 38 items above, 29 showed significant discriminant validity.
Current indicator coefficient load value averages	.79	.86	.82	.81	.87	.85	Loading coefficients to the environment >.70 support discriminant validity of the scale's dimensions (Hair et al., 2010).
Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	.62	.74	.68	.66	.75	.72	AVE >.50 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2017).
Composite Reliability (CR)	.91	.90	.93	.92	.90	.93	CR >.70 (Hair et al., 2014; Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994)
Cronbach Alpha (CA)	.86	.83	.90	.90	.84	.90	CA >.70 (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).
rho_A	.88	.85	.92	.90	.86	.92	rho_A >.70 (Çakır, 2019).
2. Validity of the Structural Model							
	DM→SPES	PG→SPES	ST→SPES	SE→SPES	AU→SPES	IM→SPES	
2.1. Standardized factor loading values	.21	.14	.28	.25	.10	.24	All path coefficients were statistically significant (p<.05). This finding supports the relationship between each sub-dimension and the whole scale (Çakır, 2019; Polat, 2018).
2.2. t-Statistics (>1.96)	10.13	13.72	17.92	14.09	5.19	18.06	
2.3. VIF	2.17	2.70	3.72	3.64	1.50	4.32	VIF <5.00 (Hair et al., 2019).

Discussion and Conclusion

In the scale development and adaptation studies of the PLS-SEM approach in the international literature (Abbasi et al., 2016; Calderon Jr et al., 2019; Calderon Jr et al., 2020; Lestari & Tentama, 2020; Mohd Dzin & Lay, 2021; Önen & Kondakçı, 2017; Quoquab & Mohammad, 2020; Silva et al., 2016) is new to use. It can be said that the academic interest in the concept of teacher empowerment in Turkey has increased with the Covid-19 pandemic. Because the pandemic period has made the importance of teacher empowerment debatable in Turkey once again (Fidan, 2021). There are already some scales developed for teacher empowerment in the national literature. Yet, it can be stated that the "School Participants Empowerment Scale" developed by Short and Rinehart (1992) is a widely used and adapted scale for many different countries, especially Malaysia (Yusoff et al., 2020). Based on this scale adaptation study, a measurement model was created with the PLS-SEM approach for the Turkish version of the "School Participants Empowerment Scale". Then, the emerging structural model of the scale was tested within the framework of Bootstrapping analysis. According to the findings; It was concluded that the Turkish version of the scale consisting of 29 items and six factors (decision making, professional development, status, self-efficacy, autonomy, influence) showed good structural model fit characteristics. It is seen that the adapted Turkish version of the scale (Annex B) has both convergent and discriminant validity. Thus, it can be said that the adapted Turkish version of the scale can be a useful measurement tool for other teacher empowerment studies in the field of educational sciences. The most important limitation of this research is the problem of whether the required and enough number of samples for the research has been reached. It is emphasized that the normal distribution condition and the small sample size should be reached as a mainstream in scale adaptation and development studies. In this case, according to Wong (2013) having a minimum number of participants between 60-75 is considered enough for analyzes PLS-SEM literature. As a matter of fact, this research was carried out on the respons of n=98 participants. Also, the respons given are limited to the opinions of the teachers participating in the research.

Implications for Further Research

Advanced organizational behavior studies can be conducted in schools in Turkey using the adapted Turkish version of the scale. Thus, it may be easier to determine the degree of teacher empowerment in educational institutions. Determining the level of teacher empowerment will be beneficial for future education policies.

Ethics Statement

All necessary permissions obtained from Muş Alparslan University Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee for this research. Date and number of ethics committee approval: 25/03/2020-E.4776.

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Appendix A.

Table 3.

Turkish version of the original scale

MN	Maddeler	Yanıtlar				
		5	4	3	2	1
1	Çalıştığım okulda bana yürütülen programları (ders, etkinlik, faaliyet, vb.) denetleme sorumluluğu verilmektedir.					
2	Gerektiğinde okul için yeni programların (ders, etkinlik, faaliyet, vb.) uygulanması ile ilgili kararlar alabilirim.					
3	İhtiyaç halinde okulda görevlendirilecek diğer öğretmenlerin seçimi konusundaki kararlarım dikkate alınır.					
4	Okulun bütçesi hakkında karar verilirken görüşüme başvurulur.					
5	Bu okuldaki diğer öğretmenlere de bir şeyler öğretme fırsatına sahibim.					
6	Çalıştığım okulda kendi ders programımı kendim belirleyebilirim.					
7	Okulumdaki yöneticiler, diğer öğretmenler ve okul personeli benden birçok konuda tavsiyede bulunmamı isterler.					
8	Bu okulda gerektiğinde kendi ders programımı oluşturabilirim.					
9	İhtiyaç halinde verdiğim tavsiyeler başkaları tarafından kabul görür.					
10	Gereken durumlarda yenilikçi fikirleri, çalıştığım okuldaki diğer öğretmenlere sunma imkânına sahibim.					
11	Mesleğim adına profesyonel bir iş ortamında çalışıyorum.					
12	Bu okulda bana bir uzman gibi davranılıyor.					
13	Çalıştığım okulda mesleki olarak kendimi geliştirme fırsatım var.					
14	Öğrencilere her konuda öncelik tanınan bir okulda çalışıyorum.					
15	Bu okulda mesleki gelişimim için sürekli öğrenme imkânlarına sahibim.					
16	Çalıştığım okuldaki diğer öğretmenlerle iş birliği yapma imkânım var.					
17	Çalıştığım okulda saygı gördüğümü düşünüyorum.					
18	Bu okuldaki işleyiş açısından çok etkili bir çalışan olduğuma inanıyorum.					
19	Okuldaki meslektaşlarıma saygı duyuyorum.					
20	Çalıştığım okulda meslektaşlarımdan destek ve saygı görüyorum.					
21	Kendi branşım ile ilgili güçlü bir bilgi birikimine sahibim.					
22	Yaptığım işte iyi olduğuma inanıyorum.					
23	Çalıştığım okulda gerçekleştirdiğim çalışmalarla öğrencilerin kendi kendine öğrenmelerine yardımcı olduğumu düşünüyorum.					
24	Ders verdiğim öğrencilerin bütün gelişimlerini desteklediğime inanıyorum.					
25	Bu okulda çalışmakla önemli bir şeyin parçası olduğumu hissediyorum.					
26	Derslerimde öğrencilerin öğrendiklerini gözlemliyorum.					
27	Öğrencilerle ders yapmanın beni mesleki açıdan her geçen gün biraz daha geliştirdiğine inanıyorum.					
28	Bu okulda yaptıklarımla bir fark ortaya koyduğumu düşünüyorum.					
29	Okuldaki günlük programıma kendim karar verebiliyorum.					
30	Ders esnasında istediğim tarzda bir öğretim yapabiliyorum.					
31	Çalıştığım okulda öğreteceğim konuyu belirlerken seçim yapma hakkına sahibim.					
32	Dersimde işleyeceğim müfredat konularıyla ilgili karar verebiliyorum.					
33	Okuldaki görevleri yerine getirme konusunda yeteneğim olduğuna inanıyorum.					
34	Okulumdaki mesleki gelişim etkinliklerine katılım sağlıyorum.					
35	Çalıştığım okula önemli bir katkı sağladığıma inanıyorum.					
36	Çalıştığım okulda aldığım kararlar dikkate alınır.					
37	Yaptıklarımla okuldaki diğer herkesi etkileme fırsatına sahip olduğumu düşünüyorum.					
38	Okuldaki diğer öğretmenler ve öğrenciler üzerinde belirgin bir etkiye sahip olduğum görüşündeyim.					

Appendix B.

Table 4.

Adapted scale final form

Boyutlar	SN	MN	Maddeler	Yanıtlar				
				5	4	3	2	1
Karar Verme (DM)	1	1	Çalıştığım okulda bana yürütülen programları (ders, etkinlik, faaliyet, vb.) denetleme sorumluluğu verilmektedir.					
	2	2	Gerektiğinde okul için yeni programların (ders, etkinlik, faaliyet, vb.) uygulanması ile ilgili kararlar alabilirim.					
	3	3	İhtiyaç halinde okulda görevlendirilecek diğer öğretmenlerin seçimi konusundaki kararlarım dikkate alınır.					
	4	5	Bu okuldaki diğer öğretmenlere de bir şeyler öğretme fırsatına sahibim.					
	5	6	Çalıştığım okulda kendi ders programımı kendim belirleyebilirim.					
	6	7	Okulumdaki yöneticiler, diğer öğretmenler ve okul personeli benden birçok konuda tavsiyede bulunmamı isterler.					
Mesleki Gelişim (PG)	7	14	Öğrencilere her konuda öncelik tanınan bir okulda çalışıyorum.					
	8	15	Bu okulda mesleki gelişimim için sürekli öğrenme imkânlarına sahibim.					
	9	16	Çalıştığım okuldaki diğer öğretmenlerle iş birliği yapma imkânım var.					
Statü (ST)	10	17	Çalıştığım okulda saygı gördüğümü düşünüyorum.					
	11	18	Bu okuldaki işleyiş açısından çok etkili bir çalışan olduğuma inanıyorum.					
	12	19	Okuldaki meslektaşlarıma saygı duyuyorum.					
	13	20	Çalıştığım okulda meslektaşlarımdan destek ve saygı görüyorum.					
	14	21	Kendi branşım ile ilgili güçlü bir bilgi birikimine sahibim.					
Öz-Yeterlik (SE)	15	22	Yaptığım işte iyi olduğuma inanıyorum.					
	16	23	Çalıştığım okulda gerçekleştirdiğim çalışmalarla öğrencilerin kendi kendine öğrenmelerine yardımcı olduğumu düşünüyorum.					
	17	24	Ders verdiğim öğrencilerin bütün gelişimlerini desteklediğime inanıyorum.					
	18	25	Bu okulda çalışmakla önemli bir şeyin parçası olduğumu hissediyorum.					
	19	26	Derslerimde öğrencilerin öğrendiklerini gözlemliyorum.					
	20	27	Öğrencilerle ders yapmanın beni mesleki açıdan her geçen gün biraz daha geliştirdiğine inanıyorum.					
Özerklik (AU)	21	28	Bu okulda yaptıklarımla bir fark ortaya koyduğumu düşünüyorum.					
	22	29	Okuldaki günlük programıma kendim karar verebiliyorum.					
	23	31	Çalıştığım okulda öğreteceğim konuyu belirlerken seçim yapma hakkına sahibim.					
Etki (IM)	24	32	Dersimde işleyeceğim müfredat konularıyla ilgili karar verebiliyorum.					
	25	33	Okuldaki görevleri yerine getirme konusunda yeteneğim olduğuna inanıyorum.					
	26	35	Çalıştığım okula önemli bir katkı sağladığıma inanıyorum.					
	27	36	Çalıştığım okulda aldığım kararlar dikkate alınır.					
	28	37	Yaptıklarımla okuldaki diğer herkesi etkileme fırsatına sahip olduğumu düşünüyorum.					
	29	38	Okuldaki diğer öğretmenler ve öğrenciler üzerinde belirgin bir etkiye sahip olduğum görüşündeyim.					

Appendix C. Adaptation permission from the authors who developed the original scale

The screenshot shows an email interface with a toolbar at the top containing icons for mail, edit, trash, delete, reply, reply all, forward, flag, and mute. The search bar shows "KIMDEN" and "Paula M.Short". The email list shows two messages:

Gönderilen - m.polat@alparslan.edu.tr Posta Kutusunda Bulunanlar

Murat POLAT (MP) | scale_adaptation_permission | Kime: pmshort@uh.edu | 9 Şubat 2020 23:31

Dear Paula M. Short,

While doing research, I came across your "School Participant Empowerment Scale" that you and James S. Rinehart developed together. If you allow me, I would like to adapt your scale for Turkish culture. Will you allow me to adapt your scale to Turkish culture? Thank you.

Best regards.

Dr. Murat Polat

Short, Paula M (PS) | Ynt: scale_adaptation_permission | Kime: Murat POLAT, Bilgi: pmshort@uh.edu | 10 Şubat 2020 12:56 | [Ayrıntılar](#)

You have permission to use the School participant Empowerment Scale in your research, adapting to Turkish culture. Please give copyright acknowledgment in all publications and presentations.

Paula Myrick Short

Sent from my iPhone

[Murat POLAT adlı kişiye ait metnin Daha Fazlasını Gör](#)